

**THE EFFECT OF OTT PLATFORMS USAGE PATTERN AMONG GEN Z: AN
EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KOTTAYAM
DISTRICT IN KERALA STATE**

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ABSTRACT

OTT is an online entertainment platform and is one of the popular platforms on the internet. The OTT platforms initially struggled to attract customers in India but eventually it started to get popular among Indian customers. After covid 19 restrictions were lifted, the OTT platforms started to face stiff competition in holding its customers as customers got other alternative options for entertainment. So, in order to retain existing customers and acquire new customers OTT platforms need to reframe its service by understanding the customer usage pattern and OTT platform influence on existing customers. The Generation Z will be next market segment which OTT platforms can target to acquire new customers. This study will help OTT players to understand the customer usage pattern and influence of OTT platforms among Generation Z with special reference to Kottayam District in Kerala.

Keyword: OTT Usage, OTT Platform, Gen Z, Covid 19, OTT influence

INTRODUCTION

The majority of the Indian population spend their time for watching movies in theatres or other entertainment shows in television. Now with the advancement of internet technology, new way of entertainment is made available through internet and that is Over The Top (OTT) media platforms. OTT platform provide various entertainment shows like movies, sports, web series etc in either recorded version or in Live streaming which can be watched by customer through their smart phones or computer systems etc by logging into the OTT platform login webpage. The variety of content in OTT platform provide flexibility to the customer to view their favourite content through their smart phone without the disturbance of others. Now artificial intelligence is being used by the OTT platform to recommend content to its users based on their previous viewing habits on the platform. Most OTT services offer a small amount of free material and need a monthly subscription cost for premium content. Generation Z are those

population who are born in between 1997 and 2012. These population group is more tech savvy than compare to previous generation population and are more likely to use OTT platform more for entertainment purpose. Also, lockdown due to covid 19 had forced many to login OTT platform to watch movies of their preferred language. The age group of generation z lies in between 9 to 25. “The pandemic independently led to a massive increase in the viewership of OTT outlets in India, while consumption of the OTT range is most elevated among the 15-35 age groups in India.” (Hindustan Times, 2022). “India is one of the leading markets for OTT services worldwide, with projected growth to be driven further by initiatives like Digital India and other government programs” (Agarwal, 2023). In Kerala, all section of economy is opened including theatre and other entertainment places. Also, many new players are entering into to the OTT market. So, the OTT players are facing competition and challenge to hold on to their existing customer. Our study will help the OTT players to understand the usage pattern of existing generation Z OTT customers with special reference to Kottayam district of Kerala state. This will in turn help the OTT players to plan their strategy for maintain good relationship with existing customer and attracting new customer.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to Gupta and Singharia, (2021, p. 42), there is “a strong impact of both customer engagement (CE) and quality of service experience (QoSE) in influencing customers willingness to continue and subscribe (WCS) streaming services in future.”

According to Priya, Mondal and Paldon, (2021, p. 674), there is a “moderating effect of consumer engagement and Intention to use in the study, revealing the higher importance of Intention to operate having an impact on subscribing Intention.”

According to Rojas, Rendon and Corrales (2019, p. 136590), “the incremental learning approach may be a suitable option when dealing with the possible changes that users may present in their OTT consumption behavior over time, and this represents an important advantage for network administrators since such approach overcomes the weakness that a traditional model presents about their incapability of adapting to new data without a new training process.”

According to Chen and He (2019, p. 254), “development of OTT business influences customer satisfaction and conversion cost through customer perceived value brought by it, thus affecting customer loyalty in the Telecom Industry.”

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To find out how often Generation Z uses OTT platforms, with a focus on the Kottayam district.
2. To identify the usage pattern of OTT among Generation Z.
3. To find out the association between OTT usage and demographic segmentation of the customer.
4. To find out the influence of OTT on Generation Z.
5. To assess the relationship between OTT frequency of usage and customer satisfaction.
6. To suggest measures to reduce the negative influence of OTT on Generation Z

RESEARCH PROBLEM

The media industry is experiencing a new player in the industry in the name of Over The Top (OTT) media companies. The OTT companies are slowly capturing the media industry market share. The OTT companies reaped maximum profit during the lockdown period of covid pandemic. With subscription revenues of ₹10,500 crore, the Indian OTT market is viewed from this angle. According to Anup Chandrasekharan, COO of IN 10 Media and Member of the CII Dakshin Steering Committee, this is anticipated to reach ₹12,000 crore by FY 2024 and ₹30,000 crore in FY 2030, with a 20 percent annual growth. (Ramesh, 2023) OTT market is growing fast and the competition among the players of OTT platform is also growing. Also, OTT platform is emerged because of digital technology transformation in media industry. Hence to understand the usage pattern of customer and influence of OTT on customer with special reference to Generation Z, the study “the usage pattern and influence of OTT platforms among gen z with special reference to Kottayam district in Kerala state” is done.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data Collection: Through direct client interaction and the use of standardized questionnaires, primary data is gathered. From the already-existing data sources, including catalogs, the internet, magazines, and newspapers, secondary data was gathered.

Population

Kottayam District residents make up the population.

Sample Size and Sampling Method: The probability sampling technique has been used for the study's purposes. 129 respondents were chosen for the study based on convenience using various demographic factors, such as age and education.

Tools and Techniques

A descriptive research methodology has been adopted and data was analysed using SPSS with various statistical techniques like descriptive statistics, Chi Square test, Correlation and Likert scale analysis.

Hypothesis:

- H₁₀: The respondents' OTT usage is not associated with demographic factors like gender or level of education.
- H₁₁: The respondents' use of over-the-top (OTT) content is associated with demographic factors like gender and educational attainment.
- H₂₀: There is no relationship between consumer satisfaction and the frequency of OTT usage.
- H₂₁: The frequency of OTT consumption and customer satisfaction are significantly related.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	66	51.2	51.2	51.2
Female	63	48.8	48.8	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 1: Respondents Gender

Interpretation: It can be inferred from the preceding descriptive data table that, of the 129 respondents, 51.2% are men and 48.8% are women.

Education

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

	Class 10 and below	12	9.3	9.3	9.3
	Class 11 and 12	19	14.7	14.7	24.0
Valid	UG	48	37.2	37.2	61.2
	PG	50	38.8	38.8	100.0
	Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Respondents Education

Interpretation: From the aforementioned descriptive statistics table, it can be inferred that, of the 129 respondents, 38.8% had PG education, 37.2% had UG education, 14.7% had class 11 or 12 education, and 9.3% had class 10 or lower education.

Account in which OTT Platform

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Netflix	35	27.1	27.1	27.1
	Disney Hotstar	24	18.6	18.6	45.7
	Amazon Prime	29	22.5	22.5	68.2
	Sony Liv	1	.8	.8	69.0
	Zee5	5	3.9	3.9	72.9
	MX Player	12	9.3	9.3	82.2
	Other	23	17.8	17.8	100.0
	Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Respondent account in various OTT platforms

Interpretation: It can be inferred from the preceding descriptive data table that 129 respondents in all, 27.1% of respondents is having account in Netflix, 22.5% of respondents is having account in Amazon Prime, 18.6% of respondents is having account in Disney Hotstar and the remaining respondents is having accounts in other OTT platforms.

Hours you spent in watching in OTT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	Less than 1hr	27	20.9	20.9	20.9
	1 - 2 hr	46	35.7	35.7	56.6
	2 - 3 hr	34	26.4	26.4	82.9
	3 - 4 hr	14	10.9	10.9	93.8
	More than 4 hr	8	6.2	6.2	100.0
	Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Respondents hours of watching in various OTT platforms.

Interpretation: It can be inferred from the preceding descriptive data table that 129 respondents in all, 35.7% of respondents is spending 1-2hrs in a day for watching in OTT, 26.4% of respondents is spending 2-3hrs in a day for watching in OTT, 20.9% of respondents is spending less than 1hr in a day for watching in OTT and the remaining 17.1% respondents is spending more than 3hrs in a day for watching in OTT platforms.

Figure 1: Respondents normal time of watching in various OTT platforms

Interpretation: It is possible to summarize the 129 respondents from the descriptive statistics table above, 44.19% of respondents normal time of watching in OTT is late night, 33.33% of respondents normal time of watching in OTT is evening time, 12.4% of respondents normal

time of watching in OTT is other and the remaining 10.08% respondents normal time of watching in OTT is day time.

Monthly Expense on OTT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Free or No Expense	66	51.2	51.2	51.2
1 - 250	34	26.4	26.4	77.5
251 - 500	17	13.2	13.2	90.7
Valid 501 - 750	8	6.2	6.2	96.9
751 - 1000	2	1.6	1.6	98.4
Above 1000	2	1.6	1.6	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 5: Respondents monthly expense on OTT platforms.

Interpretation: It is possible to summarize the 129 respondents from the descriptive statistics table above, 51.2% of respondents monthly expense on OTT is free or no expense, 26.4% of respondents monthly expense on OTT is below Rs. 250, 13.2% of respondents monthly expense on OTT is from Rs. 251 to Rs. 500, 6.2% of respondents monthly expense on OTT is from Rs. 501 to Rs. 750, 1.6% of respondents monthly expense on OTT is from Rs. 701 to Rs. 1000 and the remaining 1.6% of respondents monthly expense on OTT is above Rs. 1000.

Language Program watch the most

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
English	69	53.5	53.5	53.5
Hindi	10	7.8	7.8	61.2
Valid Malayalam	39	30.2	30.2	91.5
Others	11	8.5	8.5	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 6: Respondents mostly watched language program on OTT platforms.

Interpretation: It is possible to summarize the 129 respondents from the descriptive statistics table above, 53.5% of respondents mostly watched language program on OTT is English, 30.2% of respondents mostly watched language program on OTT is Malayalam, 7.8% of respondents mostly watched language program on OTT is Hindi and the remaining 8.5% of respondents mostly watched language program on OTT is other languages.

Type of program prefer to watch

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Action	22	17.1	17.1	17.1
Drama	17	13.2	13.2	30.2
Comedy	30	23.3	23.3	53.5
Romance	14	10.9	10.9	64.3
Horror	6	4.7	4.7	69.0
Valid Adventure	16	12.4	12.4	81.4
Animated	9	7.0	7.0	88.4
Fantasy	7	5.4	5.4	93.8
Science Fiction	4	3.1	3.1	96.9
Others	4	3.1	3.1	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 7: Respondents type of program prefer to watch on OTT platforms.

Interpretation: It is possible to summarize the 129 respondents from the descriptive statistics table above, 23.3% of respondents type of program prefer to watch on OTT is Comedy, 17.1% of respondents type of program prefer to watch on OTT is Action, 13.2% of respondents type of program prefer to watch on OTT is Drama, 12.4% of respondents type of program prefer to watch on OTT is Adventure, 10.9% of respondents type of program prefer to watch on OTT is Romance, 7.0% of respondents type of program prefer to watch on OTT is Animated, 5.4% of respondents type of program prefer to watch on OTT is Fantasy, 4.7% of respondents type of program prefer to watch on OTT is Horror, 3.1% of respondents type of program prefer to watch on OTT is Science Fiction and the remaining 3.1% of respondents type of program prefer to watch on OTT is others.

Use of specific OTT more

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Low Cost	19	14.7	14.7	14.7
Ease of Use	36	27.9	27.9	42.6
High Quality	22	17.1	17.1	59.7
Customized Videos	10	7.8	7.8	67.4
Availability of my preferred programs	19	14.7	14.7	82.2
Faster View	16	12.4	12.4	94.6
Low or No Advertisement	3	2.3	2.3	96.9
Other	4	3.1	3.1	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 8: Respondents reason for using of specific OTT platforms more.

Interpretation: It is possible to summarize the 129 respondents from the descriptive statistics table above, 27.9% of respondents reason for using of specific OTT platforms more is ease of use, 17.1% of respondents reason for using of specific OTT platforms more is high quality, 14.7% of respondents reason for using of specific OTT platforms more is low cost, 14.7% of respondents reason for using of specific OTT platforms more is availability of respondent preferred programs, 12.4% of respondents reason for using of specific OTT platforms more is faster view, 7.8% of respondents reason for using of specific OTT platforms more is customized videos, 2.3% of respondents reason for using of specific OTT platforms more is low or no advertisement and the remaining 3.1% of respondents reason for using of specific OTT platforms more is other reasons.

How often use OTT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Very Frequently	13	10.1	10.1	10.1
Frequently	41	31.8	31.8	41.9
Occasionally	56	43.4	43.4	85.3
Rarely	12	9.3	9.3	94.6
Very Rarely	7	5.4	5.4	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 9: Respondents frequency of OTT platforms usage.

Interpretation: It is possible to summarize the 129 respondents from the descriptive statistics table above, 43.4% of respondents frequency of OTT platform usage is occasionally, 31.8% of respondents frequency of OTT platform usage is frequently, 10.1% frequency of OTT platform usage is very frequently, 9.3% of respondents frequency of OTT platform usage is rarely and the remaining 5.4% of respondents frequency of OTT platform usage is very rarely. Based on the analysis of the Likert scale, it can be inferred that, among the 129 respondents, the average frequency of using OTT platforms is 3.24. That is the respondent’s frequency of OTT platforms usage on an average is occasionally.

Association between OTT usage and demographic segmentation of the customer.

Education

H0: The respondents' use of OTT and their level of education are unrelated.

H1: The respondents' use of OTT and their level of education are related.

In this case, the Chi-square test is used to examine the association between respondents' OTT usage and education.

Education * How often use OTT Crosstabulation

Count

		How often use OTT					Total
		Very Frequently	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	Very Rarely	
Education	Class 10 and below	0	8	0	4	0	12
	Class 11 and 12	5	6	6	2	0	19
	UG	2	17	20	2	7	48
	PG	6	10	30	4	0	50
Total		13	41	56	12	7	129

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	44.777 ^a	12	.000

Likelihood Ratio	48.438	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.355	1	.552
N of Valid Cases	129		

a. 12 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .65.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.589	.000
	Cramer's V	.340	.000
N of Valid Cases		129	

Table 10: Chi-Square Table (Education and Respondents OTT usage)

Interpretation: The p-value, which is 0.000, is less than 0.05 according to the Chi-Square Test table above. In light of this, we support the alternative hypothesis and reject the null. This means that respondents' use of OTT and their level of education are related or associated. As can be seen from the above table, compared to respondents with various educational backgrounds, those with postgraduate degrees are the ones who use OTT the most (92%), with usage frequency of occasionally or above. The respondents' OTT usage and education have a moderate association, as indicated by the Cramer's V value of 0.340.

Gender

H0: The respondents' OTT usage and gender is not associated.

H1: There is an association between respondents' OTT usage and gender.

In this case, the Chi-square test is used to examine the association between respondents' OTT usage and gender.

Gender * How often use OTT Crosstabulation

Count

		How often use OTT					Total
		Very Frequently	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	Very Rarely	
Gender	Male	7	23	27	4	5	66
	Female	6	18	29	8	2	63
Total		13	41	56	12	7	129

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.309 ^a	4	.507
Likelihood Ratio	3.377	4	.497
Linear-by-Linear Association	.136	1	.713
N of Valid Cases	129		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.42.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal Phi	.160	.507
Cramer's V	.160	.507
N of Valid Cases	129	

Table 11: Chi-Square Table (Gender and Respondents OTT usage)

Interpretation: The p-value, which is 0.507, is greater than 0.05 according to the Chi-Square Test table above. We therefore accept the null hypothesis. That is, there isn't any association between their use of OTT and their gender classification. The Cramer's V value is 0.160, indicating a weak association between respondents' OTT usage and their gender classification.

Frequency of usage of various OTT Services

Frequency of watching TV Show

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very Frequently	16	12.4	12.4	12.4
Frequently	30	23.3	23.3	35.7
Valid Occasionally	31	24.0	24.0	59.7
Rarely	24	18.6	18.6	78.3
Very Rarely	28	21.7	21.7	100.0

Total	129	100.0	100.0
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(Very Rarely – 1, Rarely – 2, Occasionally – 3, Frequently – 4, Very Frequently – 5)

Table 12: Respondents frequency of watching TV Shows in OTT platforms.

Interpretation: It is possible to conclude from the descriptive statistics table above that, of the 129 respondents, 24.0% of respondents frequency of watching TV Shows in OTT platforms occasionally, 23.3% of respondents frequency of watching TV Shows in OTT platforms is frequently, 12.4% of respondents frequency of watching TV Shows in OTT platforms is very frequently, 18.6% of respondents frequency of watching TV Shows in OTT platforms is rarely and the remaining 21.7% of respondents frequency of watching TV Shows in OTT platforms is very rarely. The analysis of the likert scale indicates that, among the 129 respondents, the average frequency of viewing TV shows on over-the-top (OTT) platforms is 2.86. That is the respondent’s frequency of watching TV Shows in OTT platforms on an average is occasionally.

Frequency of watching Movies

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very Frequently	51	39.5	39.5	39.5
Frequently	45	34.9	34.9	74.4
Occasionally	14	10.9	10.9	85.3
Rarely	4	3.1	3.1	88.4
Very Rarely	15	11.6	11.6	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 13: Respondents frequency of watching movies in OTT platforms.

Interpretation: : It is possible to conclude from the descriptive statistics table above that, of the 129 respondents, 39.5% of respondents frequency of watching movies in OTT platforms very frequently, 34.9% of respondents frequency of watching movies in OTT platforms is frequently, 10.9% of respondents frequency of watching movies in OTT platforms is occasionally, 3.1% of respondents frequency of watching movies in OTT platforms is rarely and the remaining 11.6% of respondents frequency of watching movies in OTT platforms is very rarely. The analysis of the likert scale indicates that, among the 129 respondents, the average frequency of watching movies shows on over-the-top (OTT) platforms is 3.87. That is the respondent’s frequency of watching movies in OTT platforms on an average is frequently.

Frequency of watching Sports

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Frequently	13	10.1	10.1
	Frequently	19	14.7	24.8
	Occasionally	31	24.0	48.8
	Rarely	27	20.9	69.8
	Very Rarely	39	30.2	100.0
	Total	129	100.0	100.0

Table 14: Respondents frequency of watching sports in OTT platforms.

Interpretation: It is possible to conclude from the descriptive statistics table above that, of the 129 respondents, 24.0% of respondents frequency of watching sports in OTT platforms occasionally, 14.7% of respondents frequency of watching sports in OTT platforms is frequently, 10.1% of respondents frequency of watching sports in OTT platforms is very frequently, 20.9% of respondents frequency of watching sports in OTT platforms is rarely and the remaining 30.2% of respondents frequency of watching sports in OTT platforms is very rarely. The analysis of the likert scale indicates that, among the 129 respondents, the average frequency of watching sports shows on over-the-top (OTT) platforms is 2.53. That is the respondent’s frequency of watching sports in OTT platforms on an average is occasionally.

Frequency of watching Games

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Frequently	14	10.9	10.9
	Frequently	12	9.3	20.2
	Occasionally	29	22.5	42.6
	Rarely	12	9.3	51.9
	Very Rarely	62	48.1	100.0
	Total	129	100.0	100.0

Table 15: Respondents frequency of watching games in OTT platforms.

Interpretation: It is possible to conclude from the descriptive statistics table above that, of the 129 respondents, 22.5% of respondents frequency of watching games in OTT platforms occasionally, 9.3% of respondents frequency of watching games in OTT platforms is frequently, 10.9% of respondents frequency of watching games in OTT platforms is very frequently, 9.3% of respondents frequency of watching games in OTT platforms is rarely and the remaining 48.1% of respondents frequency of watching games in OTT platforms is very rarely. The analysis of the likert scale indicates that, among the 129 respondents, the average frequency of watching games shows on over-the-top (OTT) platforms is 2.25. That is the respondent’s frequency of watching games in OTT platforms on an average is rarely.

Frequency of watching Cartoons

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Very Frequently	14	10.9	10.9	10.9
Frequently	21	16.3	16.3	27.1
Occasionally	22	17.1	17.1	44.2
Rarely	18	14.0	14.0	58.1
Very Rarely	54	41.9	41.9	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 16: Respondents frequency of watching cartoons in OTT platforms.

Interpretation: It is possible to conclude from the descriptive statistics table above that, of the 129 respondents, 41.9% of respondents frequency of watching cartoons in OTT platforms is very rarely, 17.1% of respondents frequency of watching cartoons in OTT platforms occasionally, 16.3% of respondents frequency of watching cartoons in OTT platforms is frequently, 10.9% of respondents frequency of watching cartoons in OTT platforms is very frequently, and 14% of respondents frequency of watching cartoons in OTT platforms is rarely. The analysis of the likert scale indicates that, among the 129 respondents, the average frequency of watching cartoons shows on over-the-top (OTT) platforms is 2.40. That is the respondent’s frequency of watching cartoons in OTT platforms on an average is rarely.

Frequency of watching Web Series

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Very Frequently	44	34.1	34.1	34.1

Frequently	37	28.7	28.7	62.8
Occasionally	13	10.1	10.1	72.9
Rarely	10	7.8	7.8	80.6
Very Rarely	25	19.4	19.4	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 17: Respondents frequency of watching web series in OTT platforms.

Interpretation: It is possible to conclude from the descriptive statistics table above that, of the 129 respondents, 34.1% of respondents frequency of watching web series in OTT platforms is very frequently, 19.4% of respondents frequency of watching web series in OTT platforms is very rarely, 10.1% of respondents frequency of watching web series in OTT platforms occasionally, 28.7% of respondents frequency of watching web series in OTT platforms is frequently, and 7.8% of respondents frequency of watching cartoons in OTT platforms is rarely. The analysis of the likert scale indicates that, among the 129 respondents, the average frequency of watching web series shows on over-the-top (OTT) platforms is 3.50. That is the respondent’s frequency of watching web series in OTT platforms on an average is frequently.

Frequency of watching Reality Shows

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very Frequently	18	14.0	14.0	14.0
Frequently	20	15.5	15.5	29.5
Occasionally	21	16.3	16.3	45.7
Rarely	21	16.3	16.3	62.0
Very Rarely	49	38.0	38.0	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 18: Respondents frequency of watching reality shows in OTT platforms.

Interpretation: It is possible to conclude from the descriptive statistics table above that, of the 129 respondents, 38% of respondents frequency of watching reality shows in OTT platforms is very rarely, 14% of respondents frequency of watching reality shows in OTT platforms is very frequently, 16.3% of respondents frequency of watching reality shows in OTT platforms occasionally, 15.5% of respondents frequency of watching reality shows in OTT platforms is frequently, and 16.3% of respondents frequency of watching reality shows in OTT platforms is rarely. The analysis of the likert scale indicates that, among the 129 respondents, the average

frequency of watching reality shows shows on over-the-top (OTT) platforms is 2.51. That is the respondent’s frequency of watching reality shows in OTT platforms on an average is occasionally.

The pros and cons of OTT

OTT allow to view pgm with family

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	31	24.0	24.0	24.0
Agree	56	43.4	43.4	67.4
Neutral	31	24.0	24.0	91.5
Disagree	9	7.0	7.0	98.4
Strongly Disagree	2	1.6	1.6	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

(Strongly Disagree – 1, Disagree – 2, Neutral – 3, Agree – 4, Strongly Agree – 5)

Table 19: View regarding OTT allow to view program with family.

Interpretation: It may be seen from the above table that 67.3 percent of the participants agree that OTT platforms allow to view program with family. From the likert scale analysis it can be summarized that out of the 129 respondents, the mean value of respondent’s view on whether OTT platforms allow to view program with family is 3.81. That is the respondents on an average agrees that OTT platforms allow to view program with family.

OTT gives more privacy in viewing pgm

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	28	21.7	21.7	21.7
Agree	68	52.7	52.7	74.4
Neutral	28	21.7	21.7	96.1
Disagree	5	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 20: View regarding OTT gives more privacy in viewing program.

Interpretation: It may be seen from the above table that 74.4 percent of the participants agree that OTT platforms gives more privacy in viewing program. From the likert scale analysis it can be summarized that out of the 129 respondents, the mean value of respondent’s view on whether OTT platforms gives more privacy in viewing program is 3.92. That is the respondents on an average agrees that OTT platforms gives more privacy in viewing program.

OTT gives flexibility in watching pgm at convenient time

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	51	39.5	39.5	39.5
Agree	43	33.3	33.3	72.9
Valid Neutral	30	23.3	23.3	96.1
Disagree	5	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 21: View regarding OTT gives flexibility in watching program at convenient time.

Interpretation: It may be seen from the above table that 72.9 percent of the participants agree that OTT platforms gives flexibility in watching program at convenient time. From the likert scale analysis it can be summarized that out of the 129 respondents, the mean value of respondent’s view on whether OTT platforms gives flexibility in watching program at convenient time is 4.08. That is the respondents on an average agrees that OTT platforms gives flexibility in watching program at convenient time.

Watching Pgm in OTT affects Studies

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	14	10.9	10.9	10.9
Agree	31	24.0	24.0	34.9
Valid Neutral	58	45.0	45.0	79.8
Disagree	18	14.0	14.0	93.8
Strongly Disagree	8	6.2	6.2	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 22: View regarding watching program in OTT affects studies.

Interpretation: It may be seen from the above table that 34.9 percent of the participants agree that watching program in OTT affects studies. From the likert scale analysis it can be summarized that out of the 129 respondents, the mean value of respondent’s view on whether watching program in OTT affects studies is 3.19. That is the respondents on an average neither agrees nor disagrees that watching program in OTT affects studies.

Socialization of Youth affected due to watching pgm in OTT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	18	14.0	14.0	14.0
Agree	51	39.5	39.5	53.5
Neutral	45	34.9	34.9	88.4
Disagree	7	5.4	5.4	93.8
Strongly Disagree	8	6.2	6.2	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 23: View regarding socialization of youth affected due to watching programs in OTT.

Interpretation: It may be seen from the above table that 53.5 percent of the participants agree that socialization of youth affected due to watching programs in OTT. From the likert scale analysis it can be summarized that out of the 129 respondents, the mean value of respondent’s view whether socialization of youth affected due to watching programs in OTT is 3.49. That is the respondents on an average agrees that socialization of youth affected due to watching programs in OTT.

Diseases amongst youth increased due to OTT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	18	14.0	14.0	14.0
Agree	33	25.6	25.6	39.5
Neutral	45	34.9	34.9	74.4
Disagree	17	13.2	13.2	87.6
Strongly Disagree	16	12.4	12.4	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 24: View regarding diseases amongst youth increased due to OTT.

Interpretation: It may be seen from the above table that 39.5 percent of the participants agree that diseases amongst youth increased due to OTT. From the likert scale analysis it can be summarized that out of the 129 respondents, the mean value of respondent’s view on whether diseases amongst youth increased due to OTT is 3.15. That is the respondents on an average neither agrees nor disagrees that diseases amongst youth increased due to OTT.

OTT has affected the revenue of Theater owners

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	49	38.0	38.0	38.0
Agree	27	20.9	20.9	58.9
Neutral	36	27.9	27.9	86.8
Disagree	15	11.6	11.6	98.4
Strongly Disagree	2	1.6	1.6	100.0
Total	129	100.0	100.0	

Table 25: View regarding OTT has affected the revenue of theatre owner.

Interpretation: It may be seen from the above table that 58.9 percent of the participants agree that OTT has affected the revenue of theatre owner. From the likert scale analysis it can be summarized that out of the 129 respondents, the mean value of respondent’s view on whether OTT has affected the revenue of theatre owner is 3.82. That is the respondents on an average agrees that OTT has affected the revenue of theatre owner.

Relationship between OTT frequency of usage and customer satisfaction

- H₂₀: There is no relationship between consumer satisfaction and the frequency of OTT usage.
- H₂₁: The frequency of OTT consumption and customer satisfaction are significantly related.

Here, we investigate if there is a meaningful relationship between customer satisfaction and OTT frequency of usage using Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation.

Correlations

		How often use OTT	Satisfied with OTT
How often use OTT	Pearson Correlation	1	.475**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	129	129
Satisfied with OTT	Pearson Correlation	.475**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	129	129

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 26: Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation Table (OTT frequency of usage and Respondents satisfaction)

Interpretation: The p-value, which is 0.000, is less than 0.05 according to the Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation table above. Thus, we are unable to accept the null hypothesis. In other words, there is a substantial correlation between customer satisfaction and the frequency of OTT consumption. The association between the frequency of OTT consumption and customer satisfaction is somewhat strong, as indicated by the Pearson correlation coefficient value of 0.475. That is the customer satisfaction increase with the increase usage of OTT.

Findings and Suggestions:

From the descriptive statistics it can be summarized that major OTT platforms used by the respondents are Netflix, Amazone prime and Disney Hotstar. In Kottayam district, majority of the generation z spend less than 3hrs a day with evening and late night as the preferred time for watching programs in OTT platform. Majority of the respondent’s monthly expense on OTT platforms is below Rs 500 and mostly watched language program on OTT is English. Comedy, action, drama, adventure and romance are the types of programs preferred by the generation z to watch in OTT platforms. Majority of the respondents reason for using of specific OTT platforms more are ease of use, high quality, low cost, faster view and availability of preferred program. Generation Z of Kottayam district frequency of OTT platforms usage on an average is occasionally with movies and web series the most preferred programs. OTT platforms can focus more on movies and web series to attract more generation Z to their platforms.

For the purpose of examining their relationship to OTT usage, two customer variables—"gender" and "education" level—were chosen. The Chi-Square Test was used to examine whether OTT consumption and demographic factors are significantly associated. It was found out that there is an association between Education and respondents OTT usage. We can see that respondents with PG education are highest users of OTT (92%) with usage frequency of occasionally or above compared to other educational background respondents. The respondents' OTT usage and education have a moderate association, as indicated by the Cramer's V value of 0.340. But there is no association between gender classification and their OTT usage. With a Cramer's V value of 0.160, the respondents' OTT usage and gender classification show just a weak association. The considerable relationship between the frequency of OTT consumption and customer satisfaction was examined using Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation. Customer satisfaction and the frequency of over-the-top (OTT) usage are significantly correlated. There is a somewhat substantial correlation between the frequency of OTT consumption and customer satisfaction, as indicated by the Pearson correlation coefficient value of 0.475. That is the customer satisfaction increase with the increase usage of OTT. So the OTT platform should promote more usage of OTT by the customer which will in turn increase the satisfaction of customer. We had done analysis on respondent view regarding OTT and found out that the respondents on an average agrees that OTT platforms allow to view program with family, OTT platforms gives more privacy in viewing program, OTT platforms gives flexibility in watching program at convenient time, socialization of youth affected due to watching programs in OTT and OTT has affected the revenue of theatre owner. But the respondents are neutral in view that watching program in OTT affects studies, and diseases amongst youth increased due to OTT. From this study, there are more benefits of OTT usage for generation Z then compared to the drawbacks. The only drawback identified is that the socialization of youth affected due to watching programs in OTT. According to Silawat, Rajpal, Silawat and Kaur (2023, p. 1), "Insomnia, melancholy, obesity, and eye disorders are becoming more common among young people. Youth academic achievement has also been impacted by web series". Based on these findings, we suggest that an awareness programs or campaigns should be conducted on balanced usage of OTT platforms by the generation Z in schools and colleges. They should be made aware about the negative influence of OTT on their life and take corrective steps to improve their socialisation which in turn help in their psychological development and maintain their physical health. Also, OTT platforms can display information about proper and balanced usage of OTT to their customer as part of their CSR activities.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings indicated that, in the case of Kerala state's Kottayam district, the generation Z frequency of OTT platforms usage is average with movies and web series the most preferred programs. So, it is suggested that OTT platforms should focus on customised movies and web series to increase their customer base in generation Z segment. There is an association between education and respondents OTT usage with PG education are highest users of OTT. There is no association between gender and respondents OTT usage. OTT platforms are advised to spread awareness about the usage of OTT among school and UG college students. Overall generation Z are reaping benefits with OTT platform services. But they are having a view that their socialisation ability has been affected by OTT usage and many research have suggested that OTT platform usage is affecting the psychological development and physical health of the young people. So, it is advised that young consumers should adapt a balanced approach in using OTT platforms with focus on maintaining their physical as well as psychological health. OTT platforms are advised to spread information regarding balanced usage of OTT to their customer as part of their CSR activities.

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